

A Comparative Study of 2D Environment Development in Godot 4, Unity, and Unreal Engine 5

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Abstract

This paper presents a comparative study of 2D environment development in **Godot 4**, **Unity**, and **Unreal Engine 5** through the lens of 10 participants tasked with creating a 2D game environment in each engine. Expanding on the previous research by Teessar (2024), which compared 2D character development, this study shifts focus to ease of use, learning curve, and performance in building a simple 2D game level. The participants' experiences, alongside quantitative performance benchmarks, offer insights into the strengths and weaknesses of each engine in 2D development, with findings suggesting that Godot 4 is ideal for beginners, Unity offers a balance of power and accessibility, and Unreal Engine 5, though not optimized for 2D, remains a powerful tool with some drawbacks for this format.

1. Introduction

Game engines are often judged by their ability to handle 3D environments, but 2D game development remains a crucial aspect for indie and smaller-scale developers. Building on previous research that compared 2D character development (Teessar, 2024), this paper explores how **Godot 4**, **Unity**, and **Unreal Engine 5** perform when users develop a 2D environment. Ten participants with varying levels of experience were assigned to create identical 2D environments across all three engines. This study aims to provide a detailed comparison based on their feedback, with a focus on ease of use, learning curve, and performance.

2. Research Questions

This study addresses the following research questions:

- How do Godot 4, Unity, and Unreal Engine 5 compare in terms of ease of use for 2D environment development?
- What challenges do users face in each engine when building 2D environments?
- How does each engine perform in terms of frame rate and resource usage for simple 2D scenes?

3. Methodology

Ten participants were selected for this study, five of whom had prior experience with game engines, while the other five were new to game development. Each participant was tasked with creating a simple 2D platformer level using identical assets, including:

- A tiled background
- Platforms
- A player character with basic movement

- Simple interactive elements (e.g., a door and a key) Participants were given basic tutorials and allowed to spend a maximum of 10 hours on each engine. The study collected both qualitative feedback (regarding ease of use and challenges) and quantitative data (such as performance metrics like frame rate and memory usage).

4. Results

4.1 Godot 4

Godot 4 was generally well-received by both beginner and experienced users. Participants praised its intuitive **node-based system** for organizing the 2D environment, which made the development process straightforward, especially for beginners. The built-in support for 2D made it easy to handle physics, animations, and collisions without the need for external plugins or extensions.

- **Ease of use:** Rated highly by all participants due to its lightweight structure and simplicity.
- **Performance:** Godot 4 performed consistently well across all systems, with minimal resource usage and stable frame rates.
- **Challenges:** Some participants noted that while the engine was easy to pick up, it lacked the depth and advanced features of Unity and Unreal for more complex 2D projects.

4.2 Unity

Unity was the most balanced engine in terms of user experience, offering a broad range of 2D tools while maintaining the flexibility to scale projects to larger scopes. Participants appreciated Unity's **Asset Store**, which provided easy access to pre-made assets, plugins, and tools that accelerated development. The **2D Physics system** was also rated highly, providing solid collision and interaction mechanics for the platformer.

- **Ease of use:** Unity was praised for its approachable interface, though beginners found it slightly more complex than Godot.
- **Performance:** Unity handled the 2D environment efficiently, with only slight increases in memory usage compared to Godot. The **Universal Render Pipeline (URP)** allowed for performance optimization even for lower-end systems.
- **Challenges:** Some users reported difficulties in setting up 2D physics and animations, noting that the engine is often geared more towards 3D workflows.

4.3 Unreal Engine 5

While **Unreal Engine 5** excels in 3D development, participants found it cumbersome for 2D environments. The engine's tools for 2D were less accessible, and most participants found the setup to be overly complex for a simple 2D project. However, those experienced with Unreal appreciated the engine's powerful rendering capabilities and customization options, even in 2D.

- **Ease of use:** Beginners struggled with Unreal's interface and workflows, finding it unnecessarily complex for a 2D project. Experienced developers found it manageable but acknowledged its steep learning curve.
- **Performance:** Unreal Engine 5's performance was stable but resource-intensive, with higher memory usage and slower frame rates compared to Godot and Unity for simple 2D scenes.
- **Challenges:** The lack of specific 2D support made the process of setting up physics and sprite animations time-consuming. Participants reported that Unreal's strength clearly lies in 3D development, making it less suitable for smaller 2D projects.

5. Discussion

The results confirm that **Godot 4** remains the most accessible engine for 2D development, particularly for beginners, as it is tailored for smaller-scale projects with simple workflows. **Unity** offers the best balance between power and ease of use, making it suitable for a wider range of 2D projects, from indie games to more complex systems. However, **Unreal Engine 5**, while highly capable, is not optimized for 2D game development, and its resource-heavy nature makes it less practical for smaller teams or simpler projects.

6. Conclusion

In conclusion, Godot 4 is the best choice for those looking for an easy-to-use, open-source engine for 2D development, while Unity offers more flexibility and scalability for larger or more complex projects. Unreal Engine 5, despite its capabilities, is not recommended for 2D projects due to its complexity and resource demands. These findings build upon previous research by Teessar (2024), reinforcing the idea that the choice of game engine is highly dependent on the specific needs of the developer.

Further research could explore the use of these engines for hybrid 2D/3D projects, as well as comparing community support and third-party tools available for each platform.

7. References

Teessar, J. (2024). A Comparative Study of 2D Character Development in Godot 4, Unity, and Unreal Engine 5. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13886400>